

VIRTUAL TESTING AND OPTIMIZATION OF DRY WOUND PRESSURE VESSELS

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SUMMARY

At the ICCM-16 conference ALE has presented a first version of its models for virtual testing of dry wound pressure vessels [1]. The present paper deals with several improvements of the virtual testing models and combining these models with automated optimization. As a result, the mass of the pressure vessel was reduced by 17%. Subsequent testing of the optimal design has confirmed the success of the present approach

Keywords: Pressure vessel, Virtual testing, Optimization, Fibre bridging

INTRODUCTION

Advanced Lightweight Engineering (ALE) has developed and patented a breakthrough technology in the production and design of composite pressure vessels [2]. The key issue in the patent is that the matrix is left out and that dry fibres are wound directly onto the liner. Advantages of this technique are production speed, recyclability, impact resistance and fire resistance. The preferred manufacturing technology of these pressure vessels is the filament winding technique. At the ICCM-16 conference ALE has presented a first version of its models for virtual testing of dry wound pressure vessels [1]. The present paper deals with several improvements of the virtual testing models and combining these models with automated optimization using the commercial software Optimus.

VIRTUAL TESTING

Simulation of filament winding

The in-house developed winding simulation software PresVes [1], has been improved. Main improvements are increased accuracy of fibre stacking and bridging predictions, increased accuracy of winding path calculations by using second order shape derivatives and significant increase of computational efficiency. The latter is of primary importance for automated optimization.

The algorithm for calculation of thickness built-up and fibre bridging are based on mapping the fibre bundles onto a 2D representation of the vessel surface. Frequent use has been made of standard convex hull algorithms. After each fibre layer, thickness built-up is calculated and the outer surface is updated accordingly. Winding simulation

for the next fibre layer is done on the updated outer surface. An example of the calculated thickness distribution and fibre path is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Example of thickness distribution and fibre bridging

FE simulation

PresVes automatically generates an input deck for the commercial FE software Abaqus. Main improvement in the FE simulation presented in [1], is the increase in numerical efficiency. This has been achieved by switching from an implicit solver to an explicit solver. Simulation time reduced from over 3 hours to less than 10 minutes.

OPTIMIZATION

The virtual testing tools have been combined with automated optimization. A typical overview of the optimization workflow is presented in Figure 2. As final result, the requested burst pressure was reached, whereas the mass was reduced by 17%. More details will follow in the full paper.

Figure 2 Typical workflow of the optimization process

CONCLUSIONS

By using in-house developed virtual testing software, combined with automated optimization, the mass of the pressure vessel was reduced by 17%. Subsequent testing of the optimal design has confirmed the success of the present approach.

References

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